

ISic2994

I.Sicily inscription 2994

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Inessa-Aetna

Place of origin (modern)

contrada Civita

Provenance

'nel casino dei Signori Ardizzone' (cda Civita is at 37.60182,
14.90788; Casino Ardizzone is at 37.587167, 14.924129

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645344

EDCS 70900784

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1035

Dubois, Laurent 2008. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile. Tome II.. Geneva. At 114

Soraci, R. 1958. Appunti di epigrafia greca e romana relativa alla regione

hyblense-inessea-adranita. *Rendiconti dell'Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Classe di Scienze morali, storiche e filologiche*. 7.13: 251-257. At 254

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